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Solving Dominating Set Problem In Unit Disk Graphs By Genetic Algorithms

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Abstract: In this paper, we use Genetic Algorithms to find the Minimum Dominating Set (MDS) of Unit Disk Graphs (UDG). UDGs are used for modelling Ad-Hoc networks and finding MDS in such graphs is a promising approach to clustering the wireless Ad-Hoc networks. The MDS problem is proved to be NP-complete. The simulation results show that the proposed algorithm outperforms the existing algorithms for finding MDS in terms of the DS size.

Keywords: Wireless Ad-Hoc networks; Backbone formation; Genetic algorithm; Dominating set.

1 Introduction

Wireless Ad-Hoc networks can be quickly deployed for many applications. Unlike wired networks, there is no physical backbone infrastructure in wireless Ad-Hoc networks. In such networks two hosts can directly communicate when they are within the range of each other, and they communicate indirectly through relaying packets by the intermediate hosts. Clustering the wireless Ad-Hoc significantly reduces the communication overhead. Finding the dominating set (DS) is a promising approach for clustering the wireless Ad-Hoc networks. A wireless Ad-Hoc network can be modelled as a Unit Disk Graph (UDG)[1]. A graph $G = (V, E)$ is a UDG if and only if its vertices can be put in one-to-one correspondence with equalized circles in a plane in such a way that an edge connects two nodes if and only if the corresponding circles intersect. In modelling a network by UDG, nodes represent the individual hosts

and an edge connects two nodes if the corresponding hosts are within the transmission range of each other.

For graph G , Dominating Set, S , is defined as a subset of V such that each node in $V-S$ is adjacent to at least one node in S . Each node in dominating set S is called a dominator node. A node of S is said to dominate itself and all its neighbours. A minimum DS (MDS) is a DS with the minimum cardinality[7]. A sample UDG and one of its dominating sets have been shown in Figure 1.

Genetic Algorithm (GA) is a stochastic search method which is inspired by natural biological evolution. It was first proposed by John Holland[8]. D.E. Goldberg has given a new dimension to GA using it in search, optimization and machine learning[9]. The basic concept of GA is designed to simulate the processes in natural system necessary for evolution, specifically for those that follow the principle of survival of the fitness, laid down by Charles Darwin.

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Figure 1: Sample unit disk graph and a dominating set

In this paper, a genetic algorithm based method is proposed to clustering the wireless Ad-Hoc networks by finding a near optimal solution to the minimum DS problem in the graph of the network. In the energy constrained Ad-Hoc and sensor networks, the proposed method helps to extend the network lifetime due to its smaller size DS compared to other DS schemas, in terms of:

- Giving better energy conservation;
- Reducing the network traffic.

The rest of this paper is organized as follows. The next section reviews the related work. Section 3 describes the proposed Genetic Algorithm and finally our simulation results are given in section 4, and we draw our conclusions in section 5.

2 Related Works

MDS problem is an NP-hard problem, and so several approximation algorithms have been proposed to find a near optimal solution to this problem in a reasonable time. Jia et al.[10]proposed a greedy distributed algorithm to construct a DS in graph G. The idea of this algorithm is to build a spanning tree T rooted at the nodes with maximum degree and grow T until all nodes are added to T and the non-leaf nodes in T form a DS. Li et al. [11]also proposed a prune-based heuristic algorithm for constructing the MDS. In this algorithm, the dominating set is initialized to the whole nodes of the graph and then each node is examined to determine whether it should be removed or retained. If eliminating a given node disconnects the induced sub graph of the connected dominating set, then it is retained and otherwise removed. One can find a good survey of some of algorithms for finding MDS in[13]

3 The Proposed Genetic Algorithm For Finding MDS(GA-DS)

We described main features of our genetic algorithm (GA) for the DS problem as follows:

3.1 Representation

The chromosome used for this problem consists of a string of bits which length is equal to the number of the nodes in the graph. Each gene in the chromosome corresponds to a node in the considered graph and the value of each gene determines whether that node is selected as a dominator node or not.

3.2 Fitness

We use a rather simple fitness function, which describes just one property of the subgraph and embed a penalizing mechanism for preventing the production of infeasible solutions. We define the fitness value of an individual, say S, in GA population as follows. If S be a feasible solution, the fitness value is equal to the number of vertices in the solution (i.e. the number of 1s occurring in the string). If S be an infeasible solution, the fitness function gives it a bad fitness such as the number of all nodes of the graph. This is to avoid selection of the chromosomes which their corresponding sub-graph is not DS, for next generation. Fitness function is shown in (1), where n is the number of nodes in the graph:

$$f(s) = \begin{cases} \sum_{j=1}^n S[j] & \text{If S is a feasible solution} \\ n & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

3.3 Selection and Crossover

Selection is motivated by the evolutionary mechanism implied by the well-known phrase "Survival of the fittest". we use elitist selection mechanism which copies the two best individuals of a population to the population of the next generation. In our proposed algorithm after two parents (chromosomes) have been selected for crossover, the GA uses stochastic uniform crossover for generating offspring.

3.4 Mutation Operators

This operator motivated by evolutionary mechanism of mutation, where a chromosome undergoes a small but important modification. We implemented and compared three type of mutation operator in proposed GA algorithm. The mutation operators which we used are described below:

3.4.1 The simple mutation operator

The simple mutation operator simply selects one vertex in the subset of vertices and changes its corresponding allele to its complement, means that one node to be added to the sub-graph or one node to be deleted from it.

3.4.2 Hypermutation (HM) Operator

The basic hypermutation heuristic that proposed by Correa, et al. [12] starts by randomly selecting a percentage of the chromosomes of the population. The algorithm then tries to improve the fitness of each of the selected chromosomes as follows. For a given node in the chromosome, the algorithm performs the change that most improves the chromosome's fitness. For an example of their representation, assume the vertex set of a given graph be labeled by $\{1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7\}$, a typical chromosome is $\{2, 3\}$ means that nodes 2, 3 selected as dominator. Note that chromosome representation in [12] is different from our representation in which the chromosome is a list of vertices in the subset. We customize the hypermutation operator for our algorithm with its particular representation. The implementation of our hypermutation algorithm is shown in Figure 2. We investigate two cases:

Case 1: If the number of 1s in the chromosome is more than or equal to half of the length of the chromosome, we use hypermutation type 1 called HM1. This algorithm deletes dominator nodes one by one via inverting its value to 0 in the chromosome, and checks that which of these changes results most improvement in the fitness of chromosome and then performs that change on the chromosome. The implementation of HM1 is shown in Figure 3.

Case 2: If the number of 1s in the chromosome is less than half of the length of the chromosome, we use hypermutation type 2 called HM2. HM2 changes a

dominator node to non dominator node and instead selects another non dominator node to be dominator. The implementation of HM2 is shown in Figure 4.

```

Data: The population
Result: The population with mutated chromosomes
Step 1: Randomly select a subset of 10% of the chromosomes from the entire population;
Step 2:
foreach chromosome  $X$  selected in Step 1 do
    if The number of 1s in  $X > n/2$  then
        | HM1( $X$ );
    else
        | HM2( $X$ );
    end
end
    
```

Figure 2: The hypermutation algorithm

We illustrate the use of these operators in our proposed algorithm by an example. Consider a graph with vertex set $\{1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7\}$, a typical chromosome is 1011011 means that nodes 1, 3, 4, 6, 7 are in the dominator set. Since the number of 1s is more than half of the length of this chromosome, HM1 is applied. This algorithm inverts the 1s one by one and so the chromosomes should be evaluated are 0011011, 1001011, 1010011, 1011001 and 1011010. Finally, the algorithm selects the change that results in maximum improvement in the fitness of the chromosome.

```

Data: The chromosome
Result: The mutated chromosome
foreach node  $j$  with value 1 in chromosome  $X$  do
    Let  $Y$  be a new chromosome with value 0 at  $j$ 'th gene;
    Calculate the fitness of  $Y$ ;
    if  $fitness(Y) < fitness(best)$  then
        | Best =  $Y$ ;
    end
end
if  $fitness(best) < fitness(X)$  then
    |  $X = best$ ;
end
Insert the new  $X$  into the population replacing the old  $X$ ;
    
```

Figure 3: The HM1 algorithm

Lets consider another chromosome such as 1010010. In this case the HM2 should be applied. The algo-

rithm first considers the first position containing 1 and changes its value to 0 and then searches for a non dominator node which making it a dominator causes maximum improvement in the fitness of the chromosome. The chromosomes that should be examined are 0110010, 0011010, 0010110, and 0010011. The drawback of this algorithm is that it takes the entire chromosome and mutates its node by node with all non dominator nodes. So it takes a lot of time and it is computationally expensive.

```

Data: The chromosome
Result: The mutated chromosome
Let H be the set of nodes in the graph that are
currently 1 in the chromosome X;
foreach i in set H do
  Best = X;
  foreach node j that has value 0 in X do
    Let Y be a new chromosome with value 1
    at j'th gene and value 0 at i'th gene;
    Calculate the fitness of Y;
    if fitness(Y) < fitness (best) then
      | Best = Y;
    end
  end
  if fitness (best) < fitness(X) then
    | X = best;
  end
end
Insert the new X into the population replacing
the old X;

```

Figure 4: The HM2 algorithm

3.4.3 KN Algorithm

We developed another heuristic which is an enhancement of algorithms described above. This algorithm uses a local optimization rather than a global optimization technique. The idea behind this algorithm is to mutate every gene with only its neighbours. The number of neighbours that are investigated (K) depends on the average degree of the network nodes. We define average degree of the network nodes as (2).

$$\alpha = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n \delta_i}{n} \quad (2)$$

In which α denotes the average degree of the network. δ_i is degree of node i and n is the number of nodes in the network.

In fact k neighbours of a given node are investigated that k is at most α , so we call this algorithm k

neighbours (KN). The implementation of KN is shown in Figure 5. Note that set H is calculated for each node in the chromosome.

```

Data: The population
Result: The population with mutated
chromosomes
Step 1: Randomly select a subset of 10% of the
chromosomes from the entire population;
Step 2;;
foreach chromosome X selected in step 1 do
  foreach node i in X that has value 1 do
    Best = X;
    Let H be the set of neighbours of node i
    that are currently 0 in the chromosome
    X(maximum cardinality of this set is
    average degree of the graph);
    foreach node j in Set h do
      Let Y be a new chromosome with
      value 1 at j'th gene and value 0 at i'th
      gene;
      Calculate the fitness of Y;
      if fitness(Y) < fitness (best) then
        | Best = Y;
      end
    end
    if fitness (best) < fitness(X) then
      | X = best;
    end
  end
  Insert the new X into the population
  replacing the old X;
end

```

Figure 5: The KN algorithm

4 Computational Results

To study the performance of our GA algorithm for solving DS problem, we have conducted simulation experiments in two groups. The first experiment involves comparing impact of applying three different mutation operators in implementation of proposed genetic algorithm on solving DS problem. The second group evaluates the results of the proposed GA with those of the best-known DS formation algorithms. The performance measures of experiment 1 are DS size and run time and in experiment 2, the performance measure is

only DS size.

In our experiments we generate random connected graphs repeatedly and run the algorithms, measuring the size of the DS. The size of the graph ranges from 60 to 200 nodes. To simulate the structure of Ad-Hoc networks, we place nodes (hosts) randomly in a square simulation area of size 100×100 units. The coordinates of the nodes are chosen uniformly in each dimension. It is assumed that the transmission range for each host is 20. The parameters of our genetic algorithm are setting as bellow: population size is equal to 100, crossover rate is 0.8 and the number of the iterations is 100.

4.1 Experiment 1

In this experiment we study the impact of applying three different mutation operators in our genetic algorithm for solving the DS problem. In this experiment we set the stalltime of the GA algorithm to 8 seconds and compare the size of the DSs produced by GA with three different mutation algorithms. The results are depicted in fig. 6. As shown in Figure 6, the GA with KN heuristic performs better than the simple mutation and hypermutation in the same amount of time. This occurs because hypermutation is trying all of the options rather than KN algorithm; therefore better results can be achieved in the same amount of time by applying KN algorithm.

Figure 6: Comparison of three mutation algorithms on the resulting backbone size

4.2 Experiment 2

In this experiment, we compare the results obtained from our proposed algorithm with the results of Jia et al.'s algorithm [10] and Li et al.'s algorithm [11] in terms of induced DS size. The results are shown in Figure 7. Our algorithm is labeled as GA-DS. From the Figure it is obvious that the size of DS constructed by GA-DS is comparable with those constructed by the best existing algorithms.

Figure 7: Comparison of the DS size for the DS-based clustering algorithms

5 CONCLUSION

In this paper, we presented a method based on genetic algorithms for solving the MDS problem in unit disk graphs. Most of the components of proposed GA are comparable to those used in a standard GA. We implemented the hypermutation heuristic concept presented by Correa, et al. [12] with some modifications to tune it for our problem. We also developed a heuristic called KN (K Neighbours) heuristic for mutation operator. Experimental results show that GA with KN heuristic works better than simple mutation and hypermutation. Furthermore we found that the proposed GA with KN heuristic also outperforms the best existing algorithms for finding MDS in UDGs.

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